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From Classroom to Reality: Using Simulation for Engineering Students' Soft Skills Development

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Abstract: *As the mission of forward-looking universities is to educate tomorrow's leaders, it is essential to develop future professionals' soft skills and communicative skills in English to meet linguistic and cultural challenges of international communication in the modern business world. Hence, soft skills development is a topical question for business and academia worldwide. Classroom simulations have proved one of the best ways for soft skills development, as they allow ESP/EAP teachers and learners to focus both on language and on real-life situations. In this paper, we present our successful experience of introducing Engineers without Borders (EWB) simulation for undergraduate and graduate ESP/EAP students. The goal of this simulation was to develop students' soft skills by creating a real-life situation of business communication with international partners. The simulation tasks included developing the writing project rationale and overview, writing emails to potential project leaders and funding organizations, advertising the project, and presenting the latter to the general public. The results of this study show that participation in the EWB simulation has helped students to develop their communication skills in English along with such soft skills as the skills of negotiation, project management, collaboration, critical and creative thinking.*

Keywords: *simulation, soft skills development, workplace communication, project management, English for Specific Purposes (ESP), English for Academic Purposes (EAP), language teaching, engineering classroom.*

1. Introduction

As the mission of forward-looking universities is to educate tomorrow's leaders, educational activities need to meet the requirements of reality as well as to equip students with skills and knowledge they can readily use in the workplace. As demonstrated in previous research (e.g., Andreas, 2018; Chan, 2019; Cimatti, 2016; Clement & Murugavel, 2015; Elizalde & Bayona, 2018; Kaewpet, 2009; Spence & Liu, 2013; Valenzuela, 2020), both English language skills and soft skills are important for future professionals to be able to achieve their long-term career goals and to communicate effectively in our globalized world.

Work-related expertise as well as soft skills are essential for one's successful career in engineering (e.g., Arnó-Macià, Aguilar-Pérez, & Tatzl, 2020; Chassidim, Almog & Mark, 2018; Van den Beemt, MacLeod, Van der Veen, Van de Ven, van Baalen, Klaassen & Boon, 2020). According to the *Dictionary of Human Resource Management*, "soft skills are the competencies that employees possess associated with activities such as customer handling, communication, problem-solving, and team working" (Heery & Noon, 2017). Regardless of this dictionary entry, there is no unanimous opinion about the exact definition of *soft skills* and about the set of skills to be considered the soft ones. For the purposes of this paper, we define *softs skills* as a combination of communication, social, and interpersonal skills as well as of different personality traits and attitudes that enable people to perform well, achieve their goals, and work with other people effectively (adapted from Robles, 2012).

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As the findings from the needs analyses conducted for various industries (e.g., Kaewpet, 2009; Lam & Chan, 2019; Cheng & Kong, 2014; Moslehifar & Ibrahim, 2012; Prachanant, 2012; Spence & Liu, 2013) confirm, effective English language communication is essential for the professionals' employability and career success. The same refers to soft skills (Chassidim et al., 2018; Devedzic, Tomic, Jovanovic, Kelly, Milikic, Dimitrijevic, Djuric & Sevarac, 2018; Garcia, Pacheco, Méndez & Calvo-Manzano, 2020; Ivanova, Mertins, Alexandrova & Baranov, 2017; Lohana, 2015; Musa, Mufti, Latiff & Amin, 2012; Pulko & Parikh, 2003). The current labor market trends suggest that the demand for critical thinking, creativity, effective collaboration, problem-solving, and leadership will continue to grow in the future (e. g. 21st century skills, 2014; Future of Jobs Survey, 2018; Lohana, 2015).

Moreover, soft skills development facilitates students' abilities to cope with linguistic and cultural challenges associated with speaking a non-native language (Rogerson-Revell, 2007). Thus, the development of soft skills in university settings not only becomes of prime importance, but it also needs to be effectively addressed in the engineering classroom. As professionals are required to effectively communicate both their abilities and potential in English (Proctor & Justice, 2014), soft skills development should become a priority for tertiary institutions in general and for ESP/EAP classes in particular; this would allow higher education institutions to bridge the gap between higher education and the labor market as well as to improve the overall quality of professional training.

To satisfy the needs for professional communication and soft skills development, the game-based approach (e.g., Garcia et al., 2020), content-based approach (e.g., Spenader, Wesely & Glynn, 2018; Tatzl, 2018; 2019), project-based learning (e.g., Chassidim et al., 2018; Musa et al., 2012), and simulations have been used to provide students with authentic knowledge and skills they can use in the workplace. For the research project presented in this paper, simulations have been chosen as an appropriate classroom methodology, as they offer effective tools for developing both communication and soft skills within an ESP/EAP course for engineers. In addition, simulations have long proven to be a successful method of introducing real-life situations into the classroom (e.g., Barger, Sutton, Roe & Gilbert, 2008; Cheng, 2007; Halleck, 2008a; 2008b; 2018; Hyland, 1993; Kuśnierek, 2015).

The necessity of engineering students' soft skills development was initially recognized at the end of the twentieth century when scholars started speaking about the need to improve engineering education by broadening the curricula which would include some simulations of the typical modern engineering workplace and which would improve future engineers' problem-solving skills (Bjorklund & Colbeck, 1999; Evans, Beakley, Crouch, & Yamaguchi, 1993; Sullivan & Baren, 1997; Woods et al., 1997).

Real-time interactive simulations have proven successful, efficient, and stimulating for engineering students (Bourgault & Lagacea, 2002). Simulation-based learning has been positively perceived by students and teachers alike (Davidovitch, Parush, & Shtub, 2006; Downing, 2001; Guikema, Ortolano, Ohshita & Collins, 2001). However, simulations for engineering students usually focused on developing one particular skill at a time, including project management (Davidovitch et al., 2006; Nembhard, Yip, & Shtub, 2009; Trevelyan, 2007), negotiation skills (Guikema et al., 2001), teamwork, and communication skills (Downing, 2001). Thus, there has been a need for designing an over-encompassing simulation that would enable engineering students to develop a whole range of soft skills in the process of participating in a meaningful project preparing them for their future employment.

Along with professional or hard skills, soft skills are recognized as a necessary prerequisite for the engineering career success; therefore, the development of these skills needs to be integrated into the modern engineering curricula (e.g., Van den Beemt et al., 2020). At the same time, the intensive globalization of the modern world has led to the necessity of exporting engineering competencies across different countries (Lucena, Downey, Jesiek, & Elber, 2008; Balcar, Šimek & Filipová, 2018). In this connection, it is possible to speak

about the importance of creating and using simulations containing intercultural components (Bourgault & Lagacea, 2002) and/or conducted internationally in the modern system of engineering education.

In response to these demands, the *Engineers without Borders* (EWB) simulation was designed as a working tool to be incorporated into the engineering curriculum for improving students' communication and soft skills. In the project discussed below, this simulation was introduced into the ESP/EAP curriculum for international undergraduate and graduate students at a large mid-western US university. Implementation of the EWB simulation proved particularly useful for increasing the participants' cross-cultural awareness, as well as for developing their project and time management, negotiation, collaboration, problem-solving, decision-making, and some other communicative and soft skills.

1.1. Literature Review

Communication needs of future engineers have long been proven by scholars (e.g., Bourgault & Lagacea, 2002; Clement & Murugavel, 2015; Davidovitch et al., 2006; Downing, 2001; Guikema et al., 2001; Kaewpet, 2009; Spence & Liu, 2013). Although these studies were conducted in different countries, they all confirmed the importance of the LSRW (Listening, Speaking, Reading, and Writing), or the four skills development for better employability and a successful career in the modern globalized world. Based on the above-mentioned research, we consider the following communicative events important for the students in their future professionals' practice:

- Listening to and understanding of instructions, presentations, and discussions;
- Speaking effectively at meetings and group discussions, delivering oral presentations, and teleconferencing;
- Reading professional texts;
- Writing emails, memos, project proposals, and business reports.

At the same time, as demonstrated by Chassidim et al., 2018; Devedzic et al., 2018; Garcia et al., 2020; Ivanova et al., 2017; Lohana, 2015; Musa et al., 2012; Pulko & Parikh, 2003, such soft skills as teamwork, creativity, communication, critical thinking, problem solving, leadership, flexibility and interpersonal skills are in high demand as well. They are expected by the employers and are considered necessary for successful careers in engineering. Self-confidence, good work attitude, motivation, willingness to learn, responsibility, management and self-management skills have also been valued in the classroom and in the workplace alike. Thus, the importance of developing students' soft skills in the classroom is obvious, which also explains the necessity of designing appropriate teaching materials and activities.

As mentioned earlier, game-based approach, content-based approach, project-based learning, and simulations have been reported advantageous in ESP/EAP classes for developing professional work-related skills. In the current project, we focus on the simulation-based approach as one of the most suitable and beneficial ways to develop students' communication and soft skills.

The simulation-based approach became highly popular in language teaching and learning in 2000s. In the present study, we follow the definition of simulation suggested by Halleck (2002, 2007a), according to which simulation is an imitation or modeling of a real-life situation in the classroom. As noted by Fanous (2012), simulations can be easily adopted to different teaching contexts and circumstances.

While both educational games and simulations provide opportunities for practice and experiential learning, simulations are often recommended as a preferable learning tool for soft skills development (e. g. Chilcott, 1996; Hamm et al., n.d.; Hyland, 1993; Petroski, 2012; Turan, 2015). As simulations are built around real-life scenarios where information governs play, they allow participants to effectively utilize information for making informed decisions (Jones & Bursens, 2015) and create a student-centered learning environment (Vlachopoulos & Makri, 2017) leading to a greater degree of student engagement. Since

engagement is one of the prerequisites to learning (Dörnyei, 2001), simulations have the potential to be among preferred classroom tasks (Lambert, 2017; Phung, 2017). The fact that the instructor's and/or peers' feedback comes after a series of decisions can be considered another important factor making simulations a convenient and effective tool for developing students' soft skills (Hussin, 2013; Petroski, 2012).

In close association with problem-based learning (e.g., Allen & Rooney, 1998; Wood & Head, 2004), simulations include elements of self-direction and collaboration aimed to advance problem-solving and decision making in order to propose a working solution for the problem in question. At the same time, simulations are effective in providing students with interactive and meaningful experiences, as they create various true-to-life situations that allow students to improve their workplace-related skills (e.g., Angelini & García-Carbonell, 2019; Halleck, 2018; Jones & Bursens, 2015; Levant et al., 2016; Turan, 2015).

Although a number of studies on the use of educational simulations in the engineering classroom have been done before (e.g., Barger, Sutton, Roe & Gilbert, 2008; Wickens & Norris, 2018), ready-to-use simulations and the research into students' attitude to them still remain scarce at present. Therefore, more well-developed teaching materials and more in-depth studies are needed to successfully develop engineering students' soft skills in the university classroom.

1.2. Aims of the study

This qualitative study was aimed at exploring the process and evaluating the efficiency of engineering students' communication skills and soft skills development in the ESP/EAP classroom with the use of the EWB simulation. Accordingly, the following research questions were addressed:

1. Which skills are trained most by this simulation?
2. Which simulation tasks are the most challenging and why?
3. To what extent do the students consider the simulation effective in preparing them for real-life workplace situations?
4. How do students assess the importance of participation in a simulation activity as a part of their ESP/EAP course?

Thus, the main purpose of this paper is to analyze the outcomes of introducing simulation into ESP/EAP classes for developing engineering students' communication and soft skills with the help of creating a real-life situation of business communication with international partners. The results of this analysis will enable us to deepen our knowledge of the major advantages of using simulations for engineering students' communication and soft skills development in the language classroom.

2. Methods

The EWB simulation was introduced into the curriculum of undergraduate and graduate courses of an American and a Russian university. The study evaluating the role of the simulation in developing students' communication and soft skills was approved by the Institutional Review Board of the US university where it was conducted and by the corresponding department of the participating Russian university. Both universities are among the largest tertiary educational institutions in their regions and offer higher education programs with a strong emphasis on engineering.

The EWB simulation was adapted by the first author from classroom materials by Dr. Gene B. Halleck of Oklahoma State University based on the *Engineers without Borders* initiative of Pennsylvania State and Oregon State Universities.

The study focused on non-native speaking students specializing in engineering and engineering business. The US university participants were taking writing courses for international undergraduate and graduate students. Their English language level was assessed by the minimum TOEFL iBT score of 65 for undergraduate students, and of 80 - for graduate students. The Russian participants of the project were taking an advanced English course for graduate students at their university; their English language proficiency

was determined as upper-intermediate or higher, based on the results of a comprehensive four-skills exam conducted by their university.

The role of the EWB simulation in developing students' communication and soft skills was analyzed with the help of classroom observations, semi-structured interviews, and reflective essays. Since it was a part of the curriculum, the classes were observed intact. However, students' participation in follow-up interviews was completely voluntary and never affected the students' grades. Also, only the essays of those students who expressed their consent were analyzed in this study.

The interviews were conducted individually with each participant by one of the researchers. They lasted 5-15 minutes and took place either right after the class or within a day after each class. The researchers were taking extensive notes during and after each interview to capture the answers of the participants in detail. The complete list of the interview questions is provided in Appendix A.

In the process of conducting the EWB simulation, the first author of this paper took the role of a full participant of the study as the person conducting the simulation. The second author took the participant-observer and co-researcher roles in the processes of simulation organization, data collection and analysis.

The data were analyzed qualitatively based on the principles of thematic coding and qualitative content analysis (Corbin & Strauss, 2015; Schreier, 2012). At the beginning, observation notes, students' oral and written interview responses and reflection essays were analyzed separately for the first and second rounds of the EWB simulation; after that, the data from the first and the second rounds were combined.

To ensure the trustworthiness of the analytic process, the data coding was done separately by the two authors. The results of the data coding completed by each of the authors were compared then; the themes that emerged in the process of coding appeared to be the same for both researchers.

Observation notes, interview responses and essays were coded to identify the themes that emerged from the data, such as teamwork, problem-solving, and technical issues (see Appendices B and C for the complete lists of the themes). The researchers coded themes without imposing preconceived categories. The identified themes were combined to form thematic groups or categories based on the frequency, emphasis, and repetition of the themes within the data obtained in this study.

2.1. Description of the Simulation

The simulation employed in this project incorporates the elements of project management and creative activities. It consists of several tasks and requires the students to:

- choose a humanitarian project that they would be willing to support;
- justify their choice by writing its rationale and overview;
- choose a project leader and write an electronic *Letter of Invitation* for him/her;
- review possible sources of funding for the chosen project and write a *Request for Funding* email;
- create an advertisement to invite volunteers to participate in the project; and
- present their humanitarian project to the public represented by other student teams.

The participants were provided with a list of humanitarian projects to choose from, several sample CVs, and a list of international organizations that offering their support for humanitarian projects. They also had an opportunity to find their own project to support, as well as to recruit somebody from their team as project leaders. The students could choose an oral presentation, an audio podcast, a video clip, a poster, or a webpage as a method of advertising the project; they were also encouraged to use their own ideas for choosing an optimal form of presenting the advertisement.

The following software was used for the writing activities included in the simulation: Word, PowerPoint, Outlook Express, Skype¹, and Google Docs. The participants used their own computers/laptops and cell phones to communicate with their partners. In the first round, students' in-class communication with overseas partners was organized via Skype. In the second round, in-class communication took place face-to-face.

The EWB simulation was conducted twice in two different settings: the first round was organized as a series of workshops for graduate students of an American and a Russian university; the second round was conducted for undergraduate students at a US university. The goal of the project was to develop students' soft skills by creating a real-life situation stimulating the students to communicate with their international partners.

The purpose of self-reflection essays, observations and interviews included gathering the necessary data and sampling the respondents' opinions. The same direct experience questions formulated in the same way and provided in the same order during each interview were asked after the simulation (see Appendix A). Semi-structured oral and written responses were gathered from 27 participants of the project.

Initially, the first simulation was planned to be conducted within the period of two weeks, with two 75-minute sessions each week. In fact, the whole simulation took three weeks, with seven sessions in total. In the process of conducting the project, the simulation timeline was changed partly because the time and effort the students needed to complete the tasks had initially been underestimated, and partly due to some technical issues described in the *Results* and the *Discussion* sections of the paper.

The simulation included:

- a preliminary session for explaining to the students the goals and tasks as well as the idea behind the simulation itself;
- five sessions of collaborative work with partners, with the authors' in-class observation of the students' activities and with the interviews with the participants conducted at the end of each session;
- final presentations of the project; and
- in-class group debriefing and post-simulation interviews conducted individually outside the class as well as self-reflection essays collected from the students within three days after the final presentations.

The EWB simulation was chosen to be introduced into the curriculum because, as can be seen from the simulation description, it comprises the activities relevant and essential to workplace communication. Successful participation in the simulation required:

- listening to and understanding of instructions, discussions and presentations;
- effective speaking at group discussions and delivering oral presentations as well as teleconferencing, since a significant portion of the participants' oral communication was conducted over video phone calls;
- reading involved such professional texts as project descriptions, specifications, CVs and required information search for creating written texts; and
- writing in its turn included emails, project proposals, and business reports.

The above-mentioned activities meet the employability needs of young professionals identified in previous studies (e.g., Clement & Murugavel, 2015; Kaewpet, 2009; Lam et al., 2014; Moslehifar & Ibrahim 2012; Prachanant, 2012; Spence & Liu, 2013).

2.2. Simulation: the first round

Participants of the first round of the simulation were six international graduate students from an American university from Saudi Arabia, South Korea, Bangladesh, China, and Mexico (2) with Arabic, Korean, Bengali, Mandarin and Spanish as their mother

¹ Skype was chosen due to its accessibility to all the student-participants in time of the simulation. Other teleconferencing platforms such as Zoom, Yandex.Telemost and others can be used.

tongues, respectively, and thirteen graduate students from a Russian university speaking Russian as their first language. All students majored in engineering, except for the two participants who majored in industrial management. The students were randomly divided into six teams consisting of three to four students each. Each team included a student from the American university and two to three Russian students. The in-class communication between the American and Russian students took place via Skype; their out-of-class communication included email exchange, working in Google Docs, and conducting Skype sessions.

The introductory session included the description of the major goals of the simulation, the necessary procedures and activities included in the simulation, and the team assignments for the project. All the sessions of the actual simulation were conducted in class, with the researchers being present and available for answering the students' questions and providing the necessary support.

The final session included the presentation of the simulation project conducted in class for the US-based students telecommunicating with the Russian students synchronously via Skype. When the simulation itself had finished, the main researcher conducted semi-structured interviews with each of the participants individually, taking notes after each interview. After that, the participants were given the same set of interview questions as a guideline to write a self-reflection essay. The written responses were collected from 18 participants of the project; the essays constituted the main data source for this research.

2.3. Simulation: the second round

The second round of the simulation was conducted at the same American university for nine international undergraduate students coming from seven different countries: Saudi Arabia (2), Kuwait, South Korea (2), Thailand, Germany, France and Mexico, speaking six different languages: Arabic (3), Korean (2), Thai, German, French and Spanish, respectively, as their mother tongues. The participants of the second round also majored in engineering. The structure of tasks for the second round was the same as that for the first round. The in-class presentations were followed by an in-class debriefing session. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with each of the participants individually within a week after the debriefing session. At the end of the second round, nine participants' essays were collected by the authors.

3. Results

To explore the process of implementing the EWB simulation into the classroom and to evaluate the efficiency of students' communication and soft skills development, field notes of in-class observations, the results of the interviews with the students and their reflective essays were analyzed.

The identified themes (see Appendices B and C for their full lists) were categorized into the anticipated and unexpected results. The data from the first and the second rounds of the simulation were similar; the themes that emerged as unexpected during the first round of the simulation were categorized as anticipated during the second simulation round data analysis.

The results of the analysis are presented below according to the research questions investigated in this study. The examples of the participants' responses to interview questions, when quoted directly, are presented in their original variant.

3.1. RQ 1: Which skills are trained most by this simulation?

The following skills have been developed by the EWB simulation and recognized by the participants: communication skills, teamwork and collaboration, negotiation skills, problem-solving, critical thinking and decision-making, creativity, management skills, cultural awareness, and helpful personality traits.

3.1.1. Communication Skills

During both rounds of the EWB simulation students participated in the activities that required the use of all four skills (LSRW) for the successful completion of the simulation tasks. As a result, all participants mentioned improvement of their

communicative skills in terms of understanding their partners' speech, conveying their own ideas more effectively, and practicing their presentation skills. In the first round of the simulation, each participant was excited to communicate online with their foreign partners using English. In the second round, all participants reported improvement of their oral presentation skills and emphasized them as an essential aspect of their language competence. As one of the participants reported, "The most important thing is communication. Without it, the project cannot be a success."

3.1.2. *Teamwork and collaboration*

Since the EWB simulation is a team project by nature, it required collaboration on tasks completion and teamwork within each activity included in the simulation. Consequently, teamwork and collaboration were mentioned as essential skills developed by all 27 participants of the project. The use of these skills was also observed in all groups in both rounds of the simulation when the groups were required to work as teams and to collaborate with their partners to complete the necessary assignments. As noted by one of the students, "We all worked together as a group inside and outside the class."

During the simulation, the groups revealed different forms of collaboration. In some groups, students created shared Google Docs and worked on them outside the class. This allowed everyone to access and contribute to the work on the assigned tasks at any time. In other groups, students split assignments into smaller tasks and then divided them among the group members to complete them outside the class and then to evaluate them as a team in class. As teachers, the authors expected all the teams to follow the first collaborative mode, but as researchers, they never interfered into the teamwork of the students. It is also worth mentioning here that, regardless of their collaborative strategies, all groups completed the necessary assignments on time.

3.1.3. *Negotiation Skills*

Negotiation was part and parcel of teamwork throughout the simulation, as the participants had to discuss with each other the assignments as well as to agree on the ways to complete them. As a result, negotiation skills were reported as the next most important kind of soft skills after teamwork; they were described as essential by two thirds of the students in the first round and by all participants of the second round of the simulation. Although communication, collaboration, teamwork, and negotiation skills are intertwined, the ability and necessity to negotiate effectively were mentioned as a separate skill by the students.

The difficulties regarding negotiation skills encountered by the participants related to the necessity of considering the opinions of all team members and to come to consensus on each topic discussed by the team. "It is never easy to balance your own ideas with other people's ideas," reported one student. "And everyone's opinion should be heard, even if it is different than yours," stated one of his peers. In addition, one of the participants confirmed that "by listening to other opinions and discussing next steps, cooperative attitude is mostly developed during the project."

3.1.4. *Problem-solving, critical thinking and decision-making*

Problem-solving, critical thinking, and decision-making were required to accomplish the goals of the EWB simulation. Without the use of these skills, it was impossible for the students to complete the task and to present the project report. Since the simulation is problem-based, critical thinking was essential in the process of finding solutions and making decisions within each stage of the activities included in the simulation. During the project, we could observe that critical thinking skills were gradually developing in all teams at a various pace, enhancing their decision-making and problem-solving skills progressively as well.

3.1.5. *Creativity*

Creativity was another aspect of students' soft skills formation; it was developed through the "Create the Advertisement" task. Although, the students had several options to advertise their projects (see the *Methods* section), almost all teams chose to design a poster as an advert. In the second round, only one team created an audio podcast for a radio

commercial as their project advertisement. “We had to be creative to make a poster,” confirmed a participant. All posters were created with the use of free online software of the students’ choice.

3.1.6. *Management skills*

Planning and scheduling as well as personal time management were the skills that the students needed to develop to succeed in the EWB simulation. The teams had to figure out how to organize their work effectively. They also had to negotiate deadlines; the latter were not always kept by all team-members, so the participants had to work collaboratively around those issues.

Managing their time properly appeared to be a challenging task for all participants of the simulation. As one of them explained, “...difficulty was managing the time; we had to be efficient to finish everything on time.” Time management issues turned out to be one of the reasons why the first round of the simulation took longer than it had been planned before. Considering the experience of the first round, the second round of the simulation was initially scheduled longer and was conducted within the planned timeframe of five class periods. This timeline appears to be ideal for the students with the upper-intermediate/advanced level of English proficiency and with minimal time-management and negotiation skills.

3.1.7. *Cultural Awareness*

Cultural awareness was among the unexpected skills developed during the EWB simulation. Although the participants came from various backgrounds and had been previously exposed to cultural diversity, the need to raise the level of their cultural awareness was observed during the simulation. On the one hand, the participants verbally acknowledged the importance of professional behavior and of showing respect to other cultures. However, the lack of knowledge about the appropriate behavioral norms led, for example, to the following student’s remark in the first round of the simulation: “My partners are very beautiful.” This comment was expressed by a Russian male participant in relation to his female team members. Such a comment could be considered a form of harassment in the USA but would typically be perceived as a friendly compliment in Russia.

3.1.8. *Personality Development*

The next unexpected outcome of the EWB simulation was the development of the participants’ personal qualities. During the interviews, 18 out of 27 participants mentioned being somewhat shy and self-conscious during the very first collaborative meeting with their partners; however, later they reported an increased degree of confidence as the project progressed. Adaptability and flexibility were also mentioned as important qualities that contributed to the success of communication and that were needed for solving the problems discussed in the EWB simulation.

The participants also reported on patience and leadership as the qualities developed during the simulation: “I definitely improved my patience. I am in general not patient, but for this kind of project I needed to be,” reported one student. “I think I’ve learned to be a bit more persistent and take leadership when needed,” commented another participant.

3.1.9. *Willingness to Help*

One more pleasantly surprising outcome of the EWB simulation was the participants’ willingness to “make a change in the world.” We suppose that it was related to the humanitarian idea behind the simulation itself. All the participants seemed to enjoy the idea of going on a humanitarian mission and of helping people to improve their lives, for example, by constructing a reliable water supply system. The students considered their project a serious undertaking that was worth implementing, which contributed to their motivation to complete all the tasks and activities of the simulation. “We all realized how important [such projects are] for people who do not have what we have and take for granted,” reported one of the students. Several other students expressed their hope that one day they could actually make a real change in the world. In this connection, it is possible to conclude that the students’ desire of changing this world for the better advances a

compelling argument against the opinion of those who criticize young people for their apathy and insensitivity towards the problems of modern society.

3.2. *RQ 2: Which simulation tasks are the most challenging and why?*

The participants of the EWB simulation faced challenges when developing each of the skills discussed above. Communication, collaboration, teamwork, negotiation, critical thinking and decision-making, creativity, and time-management all posed a certain degree of difficulty for them. For example, as one of the students noted, “Everyone’s opinion should be heard, even if it appears to be different from many other people’s opinion.”

While making a poster was the most popular choice for the project advertisement, this activity was far from the easiest one, as it required creativity and collaboration. As one of the participants pointed out, “I am not good in marketing, and no one from my group is either. Therefore, we had to find a way to do a poster by ourselves, and that was a challenging task.”

3.2.4. *Technical Issues*

Some other challenges of the simulation were associated with certain technical issues such as an unstable Internet connection, the time difference between Russia and the USA in the first round of the simulation, and the differences in students’ schedules in the second round. It had not been foreseen that these technical issues would result in a longer project time during the first round of the simulation. However, the timeline of the second round of the simulation was adapted to these issues from the very beginning.

3.3. *RQ 3: To what extent do the students consider the EWB simulation effective in preparing them for real-life workplace situations?*

The students considered the EWB simulation valuable and beneficial for their academic and professional development. Writing emails, creating posters, listening to others, and expressing opinions when discussing problems, – all these activities were recognized as useful and helpful by the students. Thus, gaining communication skills and improving English proficiency were believed to be effectively preparing students for their future endeavors.

Oral presentations accompanied by PowerPoint slides were mentioned by all the participants as the most practical tasks they completed. As one of the students explained, “The presentation was the most important part [of the simulation], I’ll make presentations for my future projects in other courses.”

The teamwork activities included in the simulation were recognized as the second most important aspect relevant to the students’ future careers. The students considered effective teamwork necessary for their professional success. As one of the participants pointed out, “team-work is important because nowadays you can’t do a ‘masterpiece’ by yourself.”

Problem-solving in a situation close to reality as well as planning the activities to be completed on time were the next aspects which were reported by students to be beneficial for them. They understood that their academic and professional life required well-developed problem-solving and time-management skills on an everyday basis. “We improve our skill to solve a real-world problem [in the simulation],” claimed one participant. Another student also mentioned that participation in the simulation helped him and his team-mates learn to plan their work on different tasks included in the project more effectively.

Cultural awareness was also rated high in terms of its relevance to the contemporary engineering environment. “I learned to work with people from different cultures, and that will be useful for my future career,” reported one of the participants of the project.

Moreover, the use of technology during the simulation also contributed to the professional development of the students. For most of the students, it was their first experience of remote collaboration on a project and the use of Skype for business meetings. For half of the undergraduates, it was their first exposure to Google Docs. Since nowadays these technologies are commonly employed for collaboration at workplace, the participants

recognized their usefulness for their successful studies and work. “[Using these technologies] I would repeat in my academic and professional life,” as one student mentioned.

Overall, all the participants considered the EWB simulation effective in preparing them for real-life workplace situations because it offered them practice in skills they would need in their future studies and professional careers.

3.4. *How do students assess the simulation as a part of their ESP/EAP course?*

The students’ overall impressions of the EWB simulation were positive. All participants demonstrated and reported high degree of satisfaction with the simulation tasks, their cooperative problem-solving experience, and the project outcomes. Their final advice for the future participants of the EWB simulation was the encouragement to participate in similar simulations.

In addition, the students suggested that, to be able to participate in a simulation effectively, their peers should enjoy the simulation itself. In their opinion, this would help the participants of the simulation stay motivated throughout the whole simulation while completing the necessary tasks and activities, which would eventually have a positive influence on the development of their soft skills as well.

4. **Discussion**

Overall, the EWB simulation has been positively evaluated by the students-participants as engaging, motivating and highly relevant to their academic and professional needs, which signifies the value of the simulation content as well as its successful implementation into the ESP/EAP classroom for both undergraduate and graduate students of different majors. The main purpose of the study described in this paper was to evaluate the role of the EWB simulation in developing students’ soft skills. As demonstrated in the *Results* section, the students recognized its usefulness for their personal and professional development, as well as for their future careers.

Communication skills helped students advance through the project, discuss their actual ideas, and come up with group decisions. As reported by one of the participants, “Through discussions we managed to work through the challenges and have good outcomes.” All the participants emphasized the importance of listening to each other, explaining their ideas clearly and effectively, and debating the possible decisions.

Communication being recognized as one of the key soft skills by an array of researchers and employers alike (e.g., see Bardovi-Harlig, Mossman, & Vellenga, 2014; Broady, 1999; Chan, 2019; Harzing, Köster, & Magner, 2011; Rogerson-Revell, 2007; Wickens & Norris, 2018), unsurprisingly turned out to be the number one theme in the analyses. The importance of communication cannot be overestimated. As one of the participants mentioned, “Knowing how to communicate is extremely important, and it is a powerful tool in a professional workplace.” This student’s observation corresponds to Burns and Moore’s (2008) and Hussin’s (2013) findings, according to which introducing simulations allows ESP/EAP students to listen to, analyze and participate in some of the typical interactions of the professional workplace. The researchers believe that this serves as a basis for improving students’ professional communication skills in English.

Another important skill developed throughout the simulation was the students’ ability to work in teams effectively. Although teamwork was seen by some participants as an easy tool for project work, it was not always smooth for the others. In one group of the first round of the simulation, the participants seemed to have adapted to each other faster than the participants in the other teams. It probably explains why that particular team finished the necessary tasks and activities earlier than the other participating teams. In this connection, we assume that adaptability was one of the key factors contributing to the success of the project. On the contrary, a different team participating in the first round of the simulation appeared to have extremely hard times when it came to a mutual agreement about almost every question discussed during the simulation. In fact, they switched from the strategy of doing everything together in shared Google Docs to the strategy of splitting larger tasks into smaller ones and assigning different parts of those tasks to different team

members so that their outcomes could be compiled together later. From our point of view, the members of that particular team lacked adaptability and flexibility as well as negotiation skills at the beginning of the simulation. Nevertheless, eventually, the project stimulated them to develop these skills needed for the successful completion of all activities included in the simulation. This allows us to conclude that the use of simulations in the language classroom can contribute to improving their participants' adaptability, flexibility, and communication efficiency resulting in increasingly effective teamwork and collaboration.

The EWB simulation in particular provides numerous opportunities for the students to develop their critical thinking skills by participating in problem-solving and decision-making activities for each and every task included in the project. As innovation and imagination are highly valued in academia and in the workplace, developing students' creative thinking skills is highly important nowadays as well; so boosting students' creativity in the EWB simulation is particularly valuable.

In their interviews, the participants of the EWB simulation mentioned the importance of time management, completing tasks on time and sticking to deadlines, which emphasizes the importance of scheduling and time management both for one's individual work and for the work in teams. In this connection, similarly to Levant et al.'s (2016) conclusion on business simulations, the use of the EWB simulation in the classroom contributes much to the development of students' time-management and project management skills.

The importance of raising students' cultural awareness and cross-cultural competence as described by Damron and Halleck (2007) became evident for the students when they communicated with their team members from different cultural, linguistic, and social backgrounds. Both the positive and the negative instances of intercultural communication revealed in the present study confirm the necessity of developing students' cultural awareness in the language classroom. They also point to the fact that the EWB simulation proves an effective tool for that. "I was pleasantly surprised when I realized that I understand my American team member and that she understands me," reported one of the Russian participants of the project. This student's remark matches Kuśnierek's (2015) conclusion, according to which participation in simulations allows students to overcome their fear of speaking in the target language, including the fear of speaking in front of people with whom they do not have a close relationship.

Interestingly, the results of the project point to the importance of recognizing students' desire to make the world a better place. This corresponds to Cote's (2007) findings, according to which such soft skills as critical thinking, self-direction, and goal setting can be effectively taught through problem-based tasks and activities, including simulations. Our data confirm and elaborate on Chilcott's (1996) statement, according to which the new skills that students acquire and the thinking they do while participating in a simulation lead to the development of more informed citizens, better prepared for playing an active productive role in the society. Furthermore, as demonstrated by some researchers (e. g. Harzing et al., 2011; Hussin, 2013; Rogerson-Revell, 2007), developing students' intercultural communication skills allows them to overcome the language barrier and makes them ready for different business communication situations which they may encounter in their future workplaces.

Additionally, the EWB simulation proved useful in terms of enhancing students' project management skills. Although the simulation did not include any explicit scheduling tasks, it had a positive influence on developing related students' skills and abilities such as personal planning, time management, scheduling of certain activities by the team members to be able to complete the necessary tasks on time and dealing with several failures to meet deadlines. Therefore, extra in-class sessions were equally important for the participants of the project along with the above-mentioned soft skills and personal qualities.

The EWB simulation facilitated personality development as well. For example, patience and leadership development has been reported by the students. These valuable

personality traits are definitely beneficial for the participants' further studies as well as for their future careers independently of their majors.

Overall, the results of this project show that the following soft skills were successfully developed with the help of the EWB simulation: communication, teamwork and collaboration, problem-solving, critical thinking and decision-making, negotiation, and management skills, and some personal qualities associated with interpersonal skills. Thus, the EWB simulation meets the needs of future professionals in various fields identified in previous studies (e.g., Chan, 2019; Clement & Murugavel, 2015; Kaewpet, 2009; Moslehifar & Ibrahim, 2012; Prachanant, 2012; Spence & Liu, 2013).

5. Conclusion

To sum up, the EWB simulation can be considered an efficient tool to successfully develop students' communication and soft skills. As demonstrated in this paper, it can be successfully incorporated into the engineering curricula, and it meets the urgent demand for improving future engineers' soft skills, including their cross-cultural awareness and intercultural communication skills.

The positive outcomes of the EWB simulation regarding the students' soft skills development confirm its benefits for the undergraduate and graduate students of engineering and non-engineering majors at university level. The results are directly connected with various activities performed by the participants during the EWB simulation. This includes the active use of all four language skills (LSRW) and modern technology, problem-based real-life situations created by the simulation, workplace-relevant outcomes or products of the simulation, students' exposure to various cultures and accents, as well as teamwork that required the use of collaboration, negotiation, and management skills.

While more research needs to be done for assessing the development of each specific soft skill, this study offers a stronger ground for the claim that simulations can be considered an effective tool for developing such soft skills as effective communication, teamwork, problem-solving, critical thinking, decision-making, negotiation, and management skills, adaptability, flexibility, confidence, and positive attitude in the ESP/EAP classroom.

Based on the results of the present study and following Andreas (2018) in attributing the leading role in developing soft skills to universities, we can conclude that the EWB simulation can be effectively implemented and recommended for developing college/university students' soft skills. In line with Phung (2017), the EWB simulation contributed to enhanced students' engagement, as it provided them with the feeling of personal relevance as well as with the opportunity to create ideas and address genuine communicative needs. Since the participants of the project discussed in this paper had different L1 backgrounds, the use of the EWB simulation was particularly helpful in developing students' essential intercultural communication skills.

Apart from the effective development of communication skills, participation in the EWB simulation helped the students to improve their time-management and negotiation skills as well as their ability to prioritize, participate in problem-solving activities, effectively work in teams, and overcome the language barrier. "I suggest education systems all over the world should have themes and ideas similar to this simulation," stated one of the participants. This and some other similar students' comments reflect their positive perception of the role of the EWB simulation in their soft skills development.

References

- 21st century skills*. (2014). The glossary of education reform. Retrieved from <http://edglossary.org/21st-century-skills/>
- Allen, R., & Rooney, P. (1998). Designing a problem-based learning environment for ESL students in business communication. *Business Communication Quarterly*, 61, 48–56. <https://doi.org/10.1177/108056999806100207>
- Andreas, S. (2018). Effects of the decline in social capital on college graduates' soft skills. *Industry and Higher Education*, 32, 47–56. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0950422217749277>
- Angelini, M.L., & García-Carbonell, A. (2019). Developing English speaking skills through simulation-based instruction. *Teaching English with Technology*, 19, 3-20. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/332705762_Developing_English_speaking_skills_through_simulation-based_instruction
- Arnó-Macià, E., Aguilar-Pérez, M., & Tatzl, D. (2020). Engineering students' perceptions of the role of ESP courses in internationalized universities. *English for Specific Purposes*, 58, 58–74. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esp.2019.12.001>
- Balcar, J., Šimek, M., & Filipová, L. (2018). Soft skills of Czech graduates. *Review of Economic Perspectives*, 18, 45-60. <https://doi.org/10.2478/revecp-2018-0003>
- Bardovi-Harlig, K., Mossman, S., & Vellenga, H.E. (2014). The effect of instruction on pragmatic routines in academic discussion. *Language Teaching Research*, 3, 324-350. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1362168814541739>
- Barger, M., Sutton, J., Roe, E., & Gilbert, R. (2008). *The Toothpick factory: A simulation game for the soft skills*. Paper presented at the ASEE (American Society for Engineering Education) Conference and Exposition, Pittsburg, Pennsylvania, USA.
- Bjorklund, S.A., & Colbeck, C.L. (1999). The view from the top: leaders' perspectives on how to involve faculty in improving engineering education. *The Proceedings of the 1999 Frontiers in Education Conference, San Juan, Puerto Rico*, 10–14 November 1999, IEEE Catalog No. 99CH37011, 117–121, <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.2168-9830.2001.tb00562.x>
- Bourgault, M., & Lagacea, D. (2002). A seminar for real-time interactive simulation of engineering projects: an innovative use of video-conferencing and IT-based educational tools. *Journal of Engineering Education*, 91, 177-183. <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.2168-9830.2002.tb00690.x>
- Broady, E. (1999). Aspects of modern language teaching in Europe [Review of the book *Aspects of modern language teaching in Europe*, W. Gewehr (Ed.)]. *Language Teaching Research*, 1, 71-78. <https://doi.org/10.1177/136216889900300105>
- Burns, A., & Moore, S. (2008). Questioning in simulated accountant–client consultations: Exploring implications for ESP teaching. *English for Specific Purposes*, 27, 322–337. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.esp.2007.12.001>
- Chan, C.S.C. (2019). Long-term workplace communication needs of business professionals: Stories from Hong Kong senior executives and their implications for ESP and higher education. *English for Specific Purposes*, 56, 68–83. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esp.2019.07.003>
- Chassidim, A., Almog, D., & Mark, S. (2018). Fostering soft skills in project-oriented learning within an agile atmosphere. *European Journal of Engineering Education*, 43, 638–650. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03043797.2017.1401595>
- Cheng, A. (2007). Simulation-based L2 writing instruction: Enhancement through genre analysis. *Simulation and Gaming*, 38, 67-82. <https://doi.org/1177/1046878106297879>
- Chilcott, J.D. (1996). Effective use of simulations in the classroom. *Creative Learning Exchange*. Retrieved from <http://static.clexchange.org/ftp/documents/implementation/IM1996-01EffectiveUseOfSims.pdf>
- Cimatti, B. (2016). Definition, development, assessment of soft skills and their role for the quality of organizations and enterprises. *International Journal for Quality Research*, 10, 97-130. <https://doi.org/10.18421/IJQR10.01-05>
- Clement, A., & Murugavel, T. (2015). English for Employability: A Case Study of the English Language Training Need Analysis for Engineering Students in India. *English language teaching*, 8, 116-125. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5539/elt.v8n2p116>

- Corbin, J., & Strauss, A. (2015). *Basics of qualitative research: Techniques and procedures for developing grounded theory*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications Inc.
- Cote, D. (2007). Problem-based learning software for students with disabilities. *Intervention in School and Clinic, 43*, 29-37. <https://doi.org/10.1177/10534512070430010401>
- Damron, R.L., & Halleck, G.B. (2007). Generating cross-cultural training data for THE UNIVERSITY GAME: A ready-to-use simulation. *Simulation and Gaming, 38*, 556-568. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1046878107308058>
- Davidovitch, L., Parush, A., & Shtub, A. (2006). Simulation-based learning in engineering education: performance and transfer in learning project management. *Journal of Engineering Education, 95*, p.289-299. <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.2168-9830.2006.tb00904.x>
- Devedzic, V., Tomic, B., Jovanovic, J., Kelly, M., Milikic, N., Dimitrijevic, S., Djuric, D., & Sevarac, Z. (2018). Metrics for students' soft skills. *Applied Measurement in Education, 31*, 283–296. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08957347.2018.1495212>
- Dörnyei, Z. (2001). The motivational basis for language learning tasks. In Robinson, P. (Ed.), *Individual differences and instructed language learning* (pp. 137–158). Amsterdam, The Netherlands: John Benjamins Publishing Company.
- Downing, C. (2001). Essential non-technical skills for teaming. *Journal of Engineering Education, 90*, 113–117. <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.2168-9830.2001.tb00577.x>
- Elizalde, R., & Bayona, S. (2018). Interpersonal relationships, leadership and other soft skills in software development projects: A systematic review. In Á. Rocha, H. Adeli, L.P. Reis, & S. Constanzo (Eds.), *Trends and advances in information systems and technologies* (pp. 3–15). Warsaw, Poland: Springer.
- Evans, D.L., Beakley, G.C., Crouch, P.E., & Yamaguchi, G.T. (1993). Attributes of engineering graduates and their impact on curriculum design. *Journal of Engineering Education, 82*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.2168-9830.1993.tb01075.x>
- Fanous, L. (2012). Teaching communicative English language in non-native contexts using simulations. *CALR Linguistics Journal, 3*, 1-9.
- Future of Jobs Survey. (2018). *World Economic Forum*. Retrieved from http://www3.weforum.org/docs/WEF_Future_of_Jobs_2018.pdf
- Garcia, I., Pacheco, C., Méndez, F., & Calvo-Manzano, J.A. (2020). The effects of game-based learning in the acquisition of “soft skills” on undergraduate software engineering courses: A systematic literature review. *Computer Applications in Engineering Education, 28*, 1327–1354. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cae.22304>
- Guikema, S., Ortolano, L., Ohshita, S.B., & Collins, P.P. (2001). Using simulation to teach negotiation processes to environmental engineers. *Journal of Engineering Education, 90*, 631-635. <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.2168-9830.2001.tb00651.x>
- Halleck, G.B. (2008a). BULLYING: A ready-to-use simulation. *Simulation and Gaming, 39*, 266-281. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1046878107310630>
- Halleck, G.B. (2007a). Guest editorial: Second language acquisition and simulation. *Simulation and Gaming, 39*, 31-34. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1046878106298466>
- Halleck, G.B. (2007b). THE ITA PROBLEM: A ready-to-use simulation. *Simulation and Gaming, 39*, 137-146. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1046878107308060>
- Halleck, G.B. (2008b). Language socialization. *Simulation and Gaming, 39*, 183-183.
- Halleck, G.B. (2018). *From headlines to role plays: How teachers can create timely 4-skills simulations*. Paper presented at the 3rd Annual Spring Forum in TESL & Applied Linguistics, Stillwater, Oklahoma, USA.
- Halleck, G.B., Moder, C.L., & Damron, R.L. (2002). Integrating a conference simulation into an ESL class. *Simulation and Gaming, 33*, 330-344. <https://doi.org/10.1177/104687810203300307>
- Hamm, R., Pinkus L., Wilkins, A., & Town, M. (n.d.). *The impact of web-based game play on soft skills education*. Retrieved from <https://www.dol.gov/odep/documents/Soft%20Skills%20Fact%20Sheet%20Final7%2015508%20compliant.pdf>

- Harzing, A-W., Köster, K., & Magner, U. (2011). Babel in business: The language barrier and its solutions in the HQ-subsiary relationship. *Journal of World Business*, 46, 279–287. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jwb.2010.07.005>
- Heery, E., & Noon, M. (2017). *A dictionary of human resource management* (3rd ed.). Oxford, The UK: Oxford University Press. Retrieved 29 Nov. 2019, from <https://www.oxfordreference.com/view/10.1093/acref/9780199298761.001.0001/acref-978019929876>
- Hussin, V. (2013). Student and teacher reflections on indirectness as a pragmatic feature of pharmacist–patient simulations. *English for Specific Purposes*, 32, 110–121. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.esp.2013.01.001>
- Hyland, K. (1993). Language learning simulations: A practical guide. *English Teaching Forum*, 31, 16-22.
- Ivanova, M., Mertins, K., Alexandrova, M., & Baranov, P. (2017). Soft skills and Moodle. *MATEC Web of Conferences*, 141, 1056 (1-5). <https://doi.org/10.1051/mateconf/201714101056>
- Jones, R., & Bursens, P. (2015). The effects of active learning environments: How simulations trigger affective learning. *European Political Science*, 14, 254–265. <https://doi.org/10.1057/eps.2015.22>
- Kaewpet, C. (2009). Communication needs of Thai civil engineering students. *English for Specific Purposes*, 28, 266-278. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esp.2009.05.002>
- Kuśnierek, A. (2015). Developing students’ speaking skills through role-play. *World Scientific News*, 1, 73-111.
- Lam, C., Cheng, W., & Kong, K.C.C. (2014). Learning English through workplace communication: An evaluation of existing resources in Hong Kong. *English for Specific Purposes*, 34, 68–78. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esp.2013.09.004>
- Lambert, C. (2017). Tasks, affect and second language performance. *Language Teaching Research*, 6, 657-664. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1362168817736644>
- Leith, M., Boyle, L., Sim, D., van der Zwet, A., Scott, G., Jimoyiannis, A., Jandrić, P., Hauge, J. B., Sultana, T. N., & Hummel, H. (2019). What’s in a game? A game-based approach to exploring 21st-century European identity and values. *Open Review of Educational Research*, 6, 12–25. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23265507.2018.1562364>
- Levant, Y., Coulmont, M., & Sandu, R. (2016). Business simulation as an active learning activity for developing soft skills. *Accounting Education*, 25, 368-395. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09639284.2016.1191272>
- Lohana, P. (2015). Soft skills for young professionals. *IEEE Engineering Management Review*, 43, 23–24. <https://doi.org/10.1109/EMR.2015.2466973>
- Lucena, J., Downey, G., Jesiek, B., & Elber, S. (2008). Competencies beyond countries: The re-organization of engineering education in the United States, Europe, and Latin America. *Journal of Engineering Education*, 97, 433-447. <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.2168-9830.2008.tb00991.x>
- Moslehifar, I., & Ibrahim, N.A. (2012). English language oral communication needs at the workplace: Feedback from Human Resource Development (HRD) trainees. *Procedia, Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 66, 529–536. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2012.11.297>
- Musa, F., Mufti, N., Latiff, R.A., & Amin, M.M. (2012). Project-based learning (PjBL): Inculcating soft skills in 21st century workplace. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 59, 565–573. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2011.05.027>
- Nembhard, D., Yip, K., & Shtub, A. (2009). Comparing competitive and cooperative strategies for learning project management. *Journal of Engineering Education*, 98, 181–192. <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.2168-9830.2009.tb01016.x>
- Petroski, A. (2012). Games vs. simulation: When simulations may be a better approach. *Training and Development*, 66, 27-29. Retrieved from <https://web.a.ebscohost.com/ehost/pdfviewer/pdfviewer?vid=1&sid=a2bf2162-ddd3-443a-8038-dde2e032cd4c%40sessionmgr4008>

- Phung, L. (2017). Task preference, affective response, and engagement in L2 use in a US university context. *Language Teaching Research*, 6, 751–766. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1362168816683561>
- Prachanant, N. (2012). Needs analysis on English language use in tourism industry. *Procedia, Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 66, 117–125. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2012.11.253>
- Proctor, D.L., & Justice, L.J. (2014). *Teaching soft skills with games and simulations*. Paper presented at the 37th AECT's (Association of Educational Communications & Technology) Annual Convention, Jacksonville, Florida.
- Pulko, S.H., & Parikh, S. (2003). Teaching “soft” skills to engineers. *International Journal of Electrical Engineering & Education*, 40, 243–254. <https://doi.org/10.7227/IJEEE.40.4.2>
- Robles, M. (2012). Executive perceptions of the top 10 soft skills needed in today's workplace. *Business and Professional Communication Quarterly*, 75, 453-465. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1080569912460400>
- Rogerson-Revell, P. (2007). Using English for international business: A European case study. *English for Specific Purposes*, 26, 103–120. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.esp.2005.12.004>
- Schreier, M. (2012). *Qualitative Content Analysis in Practice*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications, Inc.
- Shin, S., Park, J.H., & Kim, J.H. (2015). Effectiveness of patient simulation in nursing education: Meta-analysis. *Nurse Education Today*, 35, 176–182. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2014.09.009>
- Spenader, A.J., Wesely, P.M., & Glynn, C. (2018). When culture is content: Applications for content-based instruction in the world language classroom. *Language Teaching Research*, 7, 23-36, <https://doi.org/10.1177/1362168818799768>
- Spence, P., & Liu, G.Z. (2013). Engineering English and the high-tech industry: A case study of an English needs analysis of process integration engineers at a semiconductor manufacturing company in Taiwan. *English for specific purposes*, 32, 97-109. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.esp.2012.11.003>
- Springer, S., & Collins, L. (2008). Interacting inside and outside of the language classroom. *Language Teaching Research*, 1, 39-60. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1362168807084493>
- Sullivan, F.J., & Baren, R. (1997). Simulating the workplace in an engineering technology course: a rhetorical model. *Journal of Engineering Education*, 86, 279–284. <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.2168-9830.1997.tb00296.x>
- Tatzl, D. (2018). A higher-education teaching module for integrating industry content and language through online recruitment advertisements. *Studies in Second Language Learning and Teaching*, 8, 643–672. <http://dx.doi.org/10.14746/ssllt.2018.8.3.6>
- Tatzl, D. (2019). Building a model engine for language learning with tertiary engineering students. In A. Kostoulas (ed.), *Challenging boundaries in language education. Second language learning and teaching*. (pp. 121–139). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-17057-8_8
- Trevelyan, J. (2007). Technical coordination in engineering practice. *Journal of Engineering Education*, 96, 191–204. <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.2168-9830.2007.tb00929.x>
- Turan, S. (2015). Simulation-based learning: How can be used to prepare teacher? *Revista de Educação, Ciência e Cultura*, 20, 27-43. <http://dx.doi.org/10.18316/2236-6377.15.2>
- Valenzuela, V. (2020). *The exploration of employers', educators', and students' perceptions regarding the influence of soft skills for transitioning into the workforce*. University of La Verne, ProQuest Dissertations Publishing, 27739615. Retrieved from <https://search.proquest.com/docview/2385425203?pq-origsite=primo>
- Van den Beemt, A., MacLeod, M., Van der Veen, J., Van de Ven, A., van Baalen, S., Klaassen, R., & Boon, M. (2020). Interdisciplinary engineering education: A review of vision, teaching, and support. *Journal of Engineering Education*, 109, 508–555. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jee.20347>

- Vlachopoulos, D., & Makri, A. (2017). The effect of games and simulations on higher education: A systematic literature review. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 14, 1-33. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-017-0062-1>
- Volkova, N., Zinukova, N., Vlasenko, K., & Korobeinikova, T. (2020). Soft skills, their development and mastering among post-graduate students. *SHS Web of Conferences*, 75, 04002. <https://doi.org/10.1051/shsconf/20207504002>
- Wickens, J.D.J., & Norris, D.H. (2018). The imperative of soft skills development in preventive conservation practice and training. *Studies in Conservation*, 63, 301-306. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00393630.2018.1486078>
- Wood, H., & Head, M. (2004). “Just what the doctor ordered”: The application of problem-based learning to EAP. *English for Specific Purposes*, 23, 3–17. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0889-4906\(03\)00031-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0889-4906(03)00031-0)
- Woods, D., Hrymak, A., Marshall, R., Wood, P., Crowe, C., Hoffman, T., Wright, J., Taylor, P., Woodhouse, K., & Bouchard, C. (1997). Developing problem solving skills: the McMaster problem solving program. *Journal of Engineering Education*, 86, 75–91. <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.2168-9830.1997.tb00270.x>

APPENDIX A

Questions included in the interviews with the participants of the EWB simulation

1. What is your overall impression of the EWB simulation project?
2. What are the three (3) things you liked most of all about the project?
3. What was the best moment of the project for you? What would need to be done for you to be able to experience more moments like that in the future as well?
4. What were the most challenging moments of the project? What difficulties have you come across during the project? Why, in your opinion?
5. How did you respond to those challenges or how did you overcome those difficulties?
6. What was your prevailing mood throughout the project?
7. How well did you communicate with the other team-members during the project? What would need to be done to improve your communication skills?
8. What traits of character helped you fulfill the project?
9. What traits of character have you developed while participating in the simulation?
10. What are the three (3) most important things you have learned during the project?
11. What piece of advice would you give to the students planning to participate in a similar simulation project in the future?

APPENDIX B

Table 1

Themes Identified in the Process of Data Analysis in the First Round of the Simulation

Anticipated themes:	Unexpected themes:
Communication	Personal qualities
Linguistic competence	Cultural awareness
Teamwork and collaboration	Planning and scheduling
Negotiation skills	Helping other people and making a change in the world
Problem-solving, critical thinking, and decision-making	
Technical issues	

APPENDIX C

Table 2*Themes Identified in the Process of Data Analysis in the Second Round of the Simulation*

Anticipated themes:	Unexpected themes:
Communication and presentation skills	Project management
Teamwork and collaboration	Money management
Negotiation skills	Research skills
Problem-solving, critical thinking and decision-making	Leadership
Cultural awareness	Technical issues
Creativity	
Planning & scheduling	
Helping other people and making a change in the world	